

Deja vue?

Wolfgang Sassin¹

Wolfgang Sassin,

Dr-Ing,
Independent researcher,
formerly Senior Scientist of International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis
and Lecturer of Technical University Vienna
Austria

Вольфангъ Зассинъ,

докторъ-инженеръ,
независимый изслѣдователь,
въ прошломъ главный научный сотрудникъ
Международнаго института прикладнаго системнаго анализа
и лекторъ Техническаго университета Вѣны
(Австрія)

Article No and Translation / Номеръ статьи и переводъ: 020210216 ENG

Translation: English.

Translator: Alyona Bobrova, with revisions of Wolfgang Sassin.

¹ Please send the correspondence to e-mail: w.sassin@aon.at.

Permanent URL links to the article:

HANDLE: 20.500.12656/thebeacon.2.020210216

<http://thebeacon.ru/pdf/Vol.%20.%20Issue%20.%20020210216%20ENG.pdf>

Received in the original form: 14 August 2019
Review cycles: 2
1st review cycle ready: 2 October 2019
Review outcome: 3 of 3 positive
Decision: To publish with minor revisions
2nd review cycle ready: 31 October 2019
Accepted: 2 November 2019
Translation ready: 10 January 2020
Published online: 12 January 2020

HEADLINE. Civilization based upon technics and science, faces decisions that will change the global society.

ABSTRACT

Wolfgang Sassin. *Deja Vue?* In the 21st century, "humanity" is confronted with itself for the first time in history, as a consequence of an increasingly existential global crowding-out competition. „Nature" is more or less destabilized and needs human "help" because it can no longer sustain itself and at the same time "carry" billions of people. In such a critical situation, the future development of human societies must be reconsidered. Europe needs an autonomous vision of its possible role and place in view of foreseeable global challenges. Its interest must be carefully redefined in the emerging first truly global civilization. This is especially true for self-proclaimed global vanguards such as Germany. This situation is discussed in the paper.

Key words: Industrial Civilization, agricultural values, renewable source of energy, fossil energy, homo billionis, homo sapiens, German energy policy, Europe's future

THE NEW INDUSTRIAL CIVILISATION AND ITS MECHANICAL SLAVES

THE FACT THAT OUR CIVILIZATION IS FACED WITH A DECISION which, as once with Varus, at first seemed to be of a tactical nature only, but then shook the foundations of the Roman Empire, this becomes clear when we look at the highly tense global energetic

foundations which form the indispensable basis of any kind of civilization. In order to classify the current ideas and projects of energy turns for the protection of the global climate it is helpful to remember the Roman commander Varus and his fate. On the Battle of the Teutoburg Forest Wikipedia has the following information:

Under Emperor Augustus, Varus' campaign was part of an extensive project to expand the empire east of the Rhine and north of the Alps, which began in 15 BC with the campaign against the Rhaetians and Vindelians led by Augustus' stepsons Drusus and Tiberius.²

According to Wikipedia, the Roman historian Cassius Dio writes about Quinctilius Varus:

But when Quinctilius Varus took over the supreme command of the Teutons and wanted to transform them too quickly, by regulating their conditions by virtue of his authority, by giving orders to them in other ways, and especially by collecting tribute from them and their subjects, their patience came to an end (Cassius 1987, 214).

The Teutons rebelled. When Augustus received the news of Varus's defeat, he is said to have cried out to Suetonius: "*Quinctili Vare, legiones redde!* (Quinctilius Varus, return the legions!)"

2000 years later, under the popular pretext of combating "barbaric" technology, the focus is once again on official power and the collection of additional tributes. The lawsuit, this time in the opposite direction, is already looming: *Europe, billiones redde!* This time it is about the "obsolete", "dangerous" and "environmentally harmful" technologies that are to be scrapped, with the help of which Europe once grew up and was able to dominate the world. So, which technologies are to secure, indeed which ones could guarantee Europe's position in the world of the future?

Earlier civilizations were dependent on the wide availability of biomass, hydropower, wind energy, human and animal labour. That was true until the modern times. The industrial revolution and modernity initially relied on coal, later on mineral oil and natural gas. Fossil energies seemed almost "inexhaustible" at the beginning of the industrial revolution.

The industrial revolution was, strictly speaking, the second major energy revolution since the beginning of agriculture at the end of the Stone Age (Häfele and Sassin 1976; 1978). It expanded the human possibilities in an unexpected way Häfele et al. 1981, vol. 2, 32, 36–38). Starting from England, first Western Europe, later the United States and after the First World War, Russia and Japan finally began to exhibit really global influence with the aid of these civilizational options. The prerequisite for the emergence of overarching large power structures was no longer the spatial expansion of a system of rule with the aim of attracting additional human labour for civil and military projects. The growth of industrial

² https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Publius_Quinctilius_Varus

civilization “just” needed access to fossil energy deposits, that are very unevenly distributed globally. To a lesser extent, the same thing was true for those raw materials that were or are necessary for the construction of the material infrastructure and the technical artefacts of an industrial civilization: ores, phosphates, etc.

Today’s industrial civilization represents essentially a hybrid between classic great empires and a society based on mechanical slaves. In the multipolar world of the present, “great empires” face each other in existential competition. The substructure of these great empires, i.e. their mechanical slaves, live on technical energy. The reproduction behavior of this substructure is similar to that of ants or termites. As with the queens of these peoples, there are only a few large production complexes that can generate such modern slaves. The greater the proportion of slaves that has to be used for the procurement of energy in the state, the lower the reproduction rate of the slaves.

The well-being and efficiency of “queens with a court” therefore determine the sustainability and the extent of power that these empires are able to exercise. In this context, it cannot be recalled clearly enough that it was only the transformation of a few agrarian societies into industrial societies that created the problem of the division of the world into industrialized and developing countries, which is characteristic of modernity, and the associated power gap.

TWO WORLDS: ONE ANTAGONISM

THE EXISTENTIAL INTEREST OF EVERY INDUSTRIAL SOCIETY TODAY IS FOCUSED ON SECURING THE ENERGY AND RAW MATERIAL SUPPLY, just as the procurement and the defense of their “living space” was one of the central interests of earlier agricultural societies. Fossil energy and technical raw materials were and are located in areas in which they were created geologically. Such areas were mostly of no strategic importance to agricultural societies in the 18th and early 19th centuries. The expansion of the materially mediated power of the newly emerging industrial societies soon no longer depended on the conquest of the raw materials countries and the associated subjugation of their local populations. On the contrary: cultural and technical education and the political leadership of the indigenous populations turned out to be a highly debilitating concomitant effect of securing resources. Colonialism, originally geared towards controlling cheap labour, came to a dead end in the course of this development. The workers there, as well as the military auxiliary troops, not only became superfluous, they became ballast.

Two different worlds collided in everyday imperial life, not because they were necessary as complementary parts of a universal civilization that everyone had to share. The stumbling block was the disinterest in the autochthons. Natural resources were sufficient for the changing colonialism.

The internationally oriented socialism has experienced similar things painfully enough. It

came with the promise that all those won for socialism would share equally the blessings of the industrial civilization. What was overlooked was the fact that the real power does not come from political leadership, but always from the technology that can be mastered in each case. Socialism failed because its power elites did not understand the inner conditions of technological and economic development. This development lives from the races with other mechanical slave societies and it is slackening if it does not succeed in permanently maintaining a technical-scientific lead.

The survival of mechanical slave populations is not guaranteed by government management or subsidies. Rather, it is decided by human consumers. The latter do not want to be controlled or manipulated by their own elites. Consumers regularly insist on being allowed to run over to the products of foreign slaves, provided that they are only better, cheaper or more modern, regardless of which state they come from. History demonstrates that there is no ceasefire and no mercy on the market. And there are no national loyalties in industrial societies when it comes to the material.

The question of how the mechanical slaves indispensable for the survival of the majority of humanity can always be created in sufficient numbers in the future – because they live shorter than the people they are supposed to serve – and how these slaves can be fed in the future is the very question that arises today in a world whose political structures are still dominated by agricultural values.

In Germany, the current opinion seems to be that our mechanical slaves should in future be content with renewable, sustainable, locally available energy sources. Renewable forms of energy, like the classic fossil fuels, are distributed in very different qualities and quantities across the globe, however (Häfele and Sassin 1979). This means that the entire substructure of the current power structures has to be established anew with the help of the old slaves and secured in terms of power politics. The old slaves will then be disposed of. In such a case, the conditions of competition between the individual slave populations with their very different levels of performance will shift significantly. And it would not suffice to control the technical sources as has been the case so far. For with the condition "on site", the populations in the vicinity of the by no means natural "harvesters" for natural sources would also have to be controlled and "integrated".

Similarly strong locational advantages and disadvantages are foreseeable, as was observed during the development of the era of Industrial Civilization I, which was based on fossil energy.³ The path towards renewable energies, propagated as a solution to the

³ An *Industrial Civilization I* based on fossil energy must be clearly distinguished linguistically from a future *Industrial Civilization II* based on sustainable, ecologically compatible energy and raw material production, which has only been postulated so far. The characteristics of an expected, undoubtedly radically different Industrial Civilization II, especially its economic and political structures, remain completely in the dark.

For no civilization has yet allowed itself to be limited to questions of efficiency, density of use or recycling parameters, if it wanted to define itself. There is no speculation about the intellectual

climate, environmental and fossil resource problems, thus obviously leads to at least as far-reaching a change in the structures of a society and also between different societies as that which could be observed at the end of the 19th and early 20th centuries when industrialized and developing countries broke up. The conflict potential of such a fundamental change in the individual and social competitive situation is likely to be greater rather than smaller. Moreover, there are no free spaces available today to which parts of the population that cannot be fed with the knowledge and skills of the declining form of civilization could emigrate in the future.

The question of how a global economy based on the exploitation of fossil resources and based on the division of labour could be reorganized if large parts of today's world trade were to be replaced by a regionally more or less closed circular economy with very different activity potentials in each case, this question has not yet been discussed.

In any case, from such a perspective it becomes clear that the idea of equalizing global living conditions cannot be expected in this way. In a green scenario, distributive justice and comparable life chances even appear as elements of a dream world.

The even more serious change in the political balance of power - on the part of the current centers of power as well as on the part of the regions supplying others with important raw materials and energy - has not yet been considered when talking about a "green future". Large parts of the less developed countries are now benefitting from Industrial Civilization I, because royalties and windfall profits (i.e. exploration and production levies as well as prices based on the next most expensive alternatives) from energy and raw material supplies, i.e. practically taxes on nationalized natural geological deposits, are levied and actually paid by the industrialized societies to appease them.

These transfers go far beyond the amount of "development aid" flowing to the Third World. To illustrate the consequences of an energy system transformation, the question is raised, which is by no means rhetorical, as to what would happen to the stability of the societies of the Near and Middle East if the income from oil and gas supplies were to disappear within a generation without replacement.⁴

OLD WINE IN NEW BOTTLES: EUROPE AT A CROSSROADS

THE CLIMATE PROBLEM AND THE ENERGY QUESTION, in connection with the

horizon of a global, sustainable society, and certainly there are no plausible utopias. Unless one wanted to see such a blueprint in H.G. Wells' splitting of the human species into Eloi and Morlocks. Wells Eloi, the light people are kept for food by his Morlocks, underground "technicians" (Wells 2018).

⁴ E.g., the Scientific Advisory Board of the German Federal Government for Global Environmental Change (WBGU) considers it imperative to reduce the release of carbon dioxide from fossil energy by more than 80% within the next 30 years (WBGU 2011).

creeping but no less dramatic changes in the material cycles in the biosphere, they raise completely new questions for a civilization based on fossil resources, which cannot be answered at all within the form of civilization we know.

One of these questions is whether the very different ideas about the organization of power and its control can continue to exist in today's state structures if their existential foundations on a quasi-technical level reach their limits globally, or if a political attempt is made to limit them technocratically. The idea seems naïve that the core of current societies would remain unchanged if their livelihoods were to be changed within a short period of time to a system that could not be brought into line with either the existing territorial borders or existing material exchange relations, and certainly not with existing constitutional realities.

Ultimately, it is about changes in the state of societies that can only be compared with changes that have so far been brought about at best by wars of annihilation between mutually exclusive political or religious systems.

It is therefore astonishing why a few nations, above all Germany, see themselves as technical pioneers and thus, without realizing it, want to establish globally binding ideas about the proper management of the entire planet. Although the consequences of this intellectual appropriation are only vaguely discernible, they are no less serious because of this. Unfortunately, they can hardly be described verbally. For the following highly unusual conditions must probably be regarded as basic prerequisites for a redistribution of the planetary bases of life according to scientific models, the aim of which is to preserve certain climatic conditions and self-regenerating biological cycles:

1. Existential disadvantages on the planet would no longer be compensated for by wars, but by peaceful transfers of energy, raw materials, knowledge and by movement of populations. That would not be an economic exchange, but an altruism to be planned and ultimately accepted without resistance.
2. Efficiencies in the use of production factors would have to be monitored just as strictly as the economical use of their products. That requires some sort of ideocracy.
3. Individual freedom in shaping the way of dealing with the natural foundations of life and the need to protect these foundations in favor of global use, are mutually exclusive and would simply have to be accepted as a welcome intellectual compromise.

All in all, that would amount to global environmental and resource management and a uniform and undivided global power structure. The latter seems to be the Achilles's heel of the international *Green Project*.

A "successful" turnaround in the resource and climate strategy would therefore probably have a deeper impact on our current fundamental values than the only apparently major security and legitimacy problem that the public currently associates with nuclear power

plants.

It does not seem far-fetched to imagine that more rigid societies, with reference to the principle of "one man one vote", would not only dictate to the Germans one fairly close day what they are materially entitled to and in what way they have to exploit the resources and environmental capacity they are granted overall. After all, we are in the process of drafting the charter for a global uniform society - with the self-confidence that distinguishes the paragon boys. Such a charter could very well be used against the Germans, if not the Europeans as a whole. And that is unfortunately the most likely prospect for aging societies on the verge of extinction. We should not forget in this context that the ideas of a Marx and an Engel, originating in Germany, should be imposed on us from outside, in the form of a real existing socialism - a typical German experiment, for whose failure we will pay for a long time and for a long time to come

We can turn to a message in B5 Aktuell of 3 May, 2011, quoted from the homepage Greenpeace.de:

In the event of a premature nuclear phase-out, the energy companies RWE, Eon, EnBW and Vattenfall would lose enormous profits. This is shown by calculations by the environmental protection organisation Greenpeace. In the phase-out of nuclear power demanded by Greenpeace by 2015, the companies would lose around 75 billion euros compared to the agreed extension of the term. If it were switched off in 2020, it would be about 60 billion euros. Greenpeace calls on Chancellor Angela Merkel to submit to an energy concept with clearly defined cut-off dates for all nuclear plants in Germany and to say goodbye to the system for calculating the amount of electricity.

Assuming a combined tax burden of around 50% on the profits of corporations and their shareholders, the state would have to calculate between 30 and 35 billion euros in tax losses. In addition, there would be the necessary subsidies for an accelerated introduction of renewable energy sources. Taken together, these would be further burdens for the next generation to be financed through additional loans.⁵

The Green Project, grown out of the solution of the waste problem, refers to the preservation of the natural environment. Now suddenly positioned at the centre of a new, global civilisation project, this raises new questions. These go much deeper than the apparently major safety problem that the German public in particular associates with nuclear energy. For it is about the competition between the physical sustainability of more

⁵ It cannot be predicted what ecological and economic consequences the "exit" from the main civilizational techniques, i.e. from coal, oil and increasingly also from natural gas, in addition to the previously decided exit from nuclear energy, must have for a country like the German Federal Republic. The main "alternatives" and their use on a global scale are not yet known. The fact that the large-scale use of wind and solar energy in turn has massive ecological and financial consequences, which include the prosperity of entire societies right up to the abolition of the private concept of property, is only mentioned here as an aside.

than 7 and probably soon 9 to 10 billion people on the one hand and the sustainability of the only historically existing nature on the other.

NEW ROMANS, NEW BARBARIANS?

IF ONE CONSIDERS THESE DIMENSIONS, IT TURNS OUT VERY CLEARLY:

There seem to be two basic forms of coivilization that will compete with each other for a long time, and will influence each other:

- Networks of urban centers that keep themselves afloat using an artificial, highly developed and sensitive technology and that will compete for scarce resources over long distances. Rome and Carthage have exemplified such structures.

and next to it

- marginalized clans living "close to nature", which cannot be assigned to any fixed system, new "barbarians", in other words, who can migrate because they have nothing to defend but naked life, and who, on a changing planet, are perceived from an urban point of view only as asymmetric forces that can be mistaken. The conquest of the two Americas by the "industrializing white man" and the perception of this imposed yoke by the indigenous peoples, they illustrate the other side of history.

As in the past, the erection of border walls and as their tacit prerequisite mental exclusion is imminent if immigration into the overcrowded urban civilization has to be limited out of existential necessity. If this defence begins too late, inner ghettos will emerge instead of Chinese walls. Mirrored by this, piracy and terrorist attacks on the "tentacles of the urban world" are the precarious people's answer. (Mullin and Ledwith 2015).

Over the next one or two generations, the "humanity" will be replenished with an additional 2 or 3 billion of its new members. Let us turn to the data from the World Population Report (Fig. 1-2). The eight billion mark will soon be passed: As society ages in Germany, the population is growing worldwide. The World Population Report sums it up in numbers. Renate Bähr from the World Population Foundation warns in an interview with *tagesschau.de* about a "spiral of poverty." We face the problem of uncontrolled migration of non-European tribes from the nearest Mediterranean to the EU, especially to Germany. With new billions born in the Middle East and Africa, Germany will face collapse unless a stringent migration policy is developed. (Fuchs 2018).

Fig. 1. UN World Population Report.
© tagesschau.de

Fig. 2. Supposed growth of the world population. The prognosis to 2050 is nine billion humans.
© tagesschau.de

Asia + 1064 mln
Africa + 965 mln
Latin America + 140 mln
North Amerika + 96mln
Europe -42 mln,
particularly for Germany -11 mln

Such ramparts have never been completely sealed off. Ultimately, they could and should only differentiate between different forms of legal understanding. The example of Rome teaches us that as supposed “eternal high-tech townspeople” we could also be governed

by “soldier emperors” who served as immigrants, in the dirty business of defending the supply lines in the distant country, gained power and influence and finally as “Roman citizens” have corrupted the “rule for the benefit of all” system.

We should see that with the energy turnaround that has now been brought into consciousness and with the principle of opening the door to every laden person, which is held up at the same time, the course for the future of Europe will be set for a very long time and determined in a very special way. Such a course-setting must lead to an epochal dichotomy:

As Europeans, we are about to move into a global diaspora, which would make us itinerant preachers, like those officers in the Roman army who once converted to Christianity and no longer wanted to serve their economically driven war machine. If we want to avoid becoming an internal threat to the survival of our still supporting, technically based empire on such a stony path, and on the other hand, we don't want to run over to those cohorts who blindly defend this empire with all means, no matter how long it can still exist, then there is only one thing left to do:

To look for a sufficiently large niche instead of wanting to redeem the entire globe. Europe must reflect on itself and clearly set itself apart from those civilizing latecomers whose “catch-up needs” endanger its own existence and, in the long run, that of everyone. And it is precisely this realization that seems to be particularly difficult for the Germans, as well as their western neighbors.

In any case, we have to take enough time to decide where to go. Such truly historical a decision cannot be made indirectly through the choice of preferred energy sources for moral reasons. And it can never succeed without close European allies (Sassin 2015). We should, therefore, open our eyes and accept that „the global society“ has long been divided since the beginning of industrialization, a situation that even Constantine⁶ could not reverse if he elevated altruism to the state religion instead of a cool mind. And we have to make it clear that freedom of belief – and shortly afterwards freedom of knowledge, as well as the last free majority decision in any society will go overboard by decree, if prosperity erodes in the end.

The European debt crisis and its effects on the fringes of urban Europe leave no doubt: we will not escape the construction of new borders, i.e. new border walls, because transfers to the “barbarian areas” only create new competitors for scarcer resources and they always weaken the old centers (Sassin 2012). The main goal of our development policy should, therefore, be strictly preventive for any further growth of the global *precarium*. This idea has so far remained a political taboo, probably because we are only too happy to fall into the fallacy that Rome could have saved itself with a perpetuated URBI et ORBI; in other words, with the program of first subjugating the entire world circle in order to enforce the Pax Romana and in a second step to cultivate the incorporated barbarians.

⁶ Constantine the Great, a Roman emperor from 306 to 337, ended the persecution of Christians and officially recognized and approved Christianity as the state religion.

The USA is currently abandoning similar attempts. They limit themselves to wars against terrorists, and no longer pursue the expansion of their constitution, an endeavor they could only "win" economically as Pyrrhus once did. Europe should, therefore, carefully examine and convey to its citizens the following maxim:

We need to be clear about which of the mutually exclusive forms of civilizations we want to join and what the consequences will be for us Europeans, in particular for the Germans. Because it is not just about technical decisions, such as an energy turnaround or the survival of certain currencies. Rather, the question is whether we will start such a basic experiment, which we will not stop halfway through, and which will determine Europe's chances in a world that usually does not tolerate mistakes. Fukushima teaches us – if we may still be taught anything – this.

CIVILIZATIONAL CONDITIONS

THE GLOBAL GROWTH OF *HOMO SAPIENS SAPIENS* has brought about a profound conflict between the scientific-technological civilization, on the one hand, and biological and physiological processes, on the other. The latter not only forms the basis of human life. These processes also represent the self-controlling basis for life on the planet in general, an insight that James Lovelock (2016) originally expressed with his GAIA hypothesis.

The idea of a natural meeting-point for the purpose of neighbourly exchange adheres to village commons. These were accessible to all the villagers, and to a limited extent to passing strangers. Such places were always connected by public rights of way. Also on those pathways the following applied: everyone was allowed to stay as long as he moved. Hostels had to accommodate the travelling strangers; in this respect they were public and allowed the control of strangers.

All other land used was private in agricultural communities and closed to third party access. This principle of any civilization bound to fixed resources is still valid today in urban areas.

Because of the high density in urban areas, which was historically accepted because of its defensibility against enemy attacks, a kind of MIXED FORM of public space developed in the cities: commercial uses developed in it that were no longer limited to the classical marketplaces and bazaars. The credo "Stadtluft macht frei" has, in addition to the legal peculiarity, namely the abolition of the jurisdiction of the feudal lords, also had a very practical aspect: Everyone could stay anywhere in the city's public space, which had been expanded in this way, without being immediately identified as a stranger and placed under observation. Socially disadvantaged people as a not to be excluded element of a society are therefore a result of the urban way of life. The right of residence in the city has been successively separated from the ability to care for oneself. This is the main reason for the rural exodus into the "promised cities", a process that takes place at a higher rate

the higher the birth surplus in rural societies.

With "life-filled pedestrian zones", attempts are being made today in the industrial nations to satisfy the need for neighbourly exchange in the urban zone and to overcome the anonymity of modern urban life at least to some extent. The village thus returns to the city in a rudimentary form. Such places, however, do not tolerate a state of anonymized locomotion. Hence the banishment of others as "natural" means of transport. Trolleys and carts, even bicycles disturb. Conversely, the urban way of life today visibly intervenes in the way of life of the "village", i.e. the original habitat of an agricultural civilization. This begins with the development of large agricultural enterprises. It continues via traffic and supply roads that not only cut up private spaces but also have a direct effect on private spaces. In addition, these routes pose a risk, some of which is considerable. A new dimension of this intrusion into the private sphere is being initiated with the widespread introduction of renewable energies, which are now suddenly establishing businesses in the immediate vicinity of the home and also public encounters, with all its implications, including the partial opening of private space for access, control and monitoring of the installations there by service personnel and state surveillance.

It is questionable how far the return of the urban to the rural area can go. Ultimately, too much of each other destroys all the advantages of the other model. Another aspect of the creeping blurring of a clear distinction between public and private is usually ignored in this context: the move of the precariat into established orders. It is the mirror image of the process of the penetration of industrial societies into agrarian societies, which was connected with colonization, and whose spatial and communication model was thus destroyed. This process has indeed ended with the dissolution of the colonial empires. The modern form of project development via capital accumulation points and the transformation of entire regions, both urban and rural structures, which is possible as a result, shows clear parallels to the phenomenon of colonization.

Against this background, the mixing of cultural groupings through migration, which differ above all in their understanding of space and the related communication patterns, shows one thing quite clearly:

The problem of land grabbing in foreign territory was peacefully possible in agricultural societies only by reclamation of unused land. Forests and fallow land remained there in a state of suspense between nomadic and agrarian spatial understanding. The "gypsies" and the outlaws settled in this limbo. A similar critical situation is developing today in the slums. It is a continuation of the conflict-laden competition between the spatial concept of the productive sedentary and the more archaic camp concept of nomads, i.e. the non-settled and non-productive, as it was once triggered by Sinti and Roma in agrarian societies. Today, this conflict is carried into our industrial urban life in the same way by migrants from cultural circles, who for their part have not yet really mastered the cultural rupture caused by the migration of parents and grandparents from the countryside. There is no better way to see this than in the phenomenon of the leisure society.

In the urban centers a similar conflict has developed in everyday life. It manifests itself

in the extreme in the occupation of houses by autonomous people, less visible but much more problematic by a weak form of ghettoisation triggered by low-income immigrants and by autochthonous drop-outs. They pose insoluble legal problems for the regulatory authorities. For most constitutions simply negate the fact that existential need does not, in principle, stop at law. This continues until finally poverty is declared the enemy and the enemy is kept away by force. Border fences and pogroms are always the result of earlier looking-away, - or should one formulate more precisely: They are the inevitable result of earlier tolerance and compassion.

SOCIAL ORDER IN A WORLD WITH STRONG ECONOMIC AND COMMUNICATIVE INTERDEPENDENCIES

HOW FAR THE “GREAT FREEDOMS” OF THE EU CAN GO WITHOUT CREATING MORE PROBLEMS THAN THEY SOLVE, IS THE CENTRAL QUESTION whose answer will determine Europe’s future. In this regard, the European political project is really an open experiment. Europe can only become a model for other regions if it can find a persuasive answer to this question – the answer that would almost completely convince the European population. If it does not succeed, old Europe will sink into conflict and irrelevance. After all, such experiments cannot be undone without leaving a political and social pile of rubble.

The unification of Europe, in particular its enlargement without the use of force, only appears to be a peaceful process. Because every political unification process requires the submission of the citizens to politically enforceable power structures, which in principle mean interventions at the expense of an ever shrinking proportion of productive citizens. The resulting transfer systems have to continue to proliferate the tendencies created by elections. With each ballot, additional promises that go beyond the previous promises are necessary in order to win votes again. The democratic principle therefore requires an ever deeper accumulation of power by the state. In order to be able to keep the mechanism of this incessantly growing demand for the shaping of the state going, ever bolder visions are required as a justification for even more state. However, the advantages of an enlargement and deepening of the Community promised to the electorate with Maastricht and later Lisbon, namely more and more far-reaching freedoms, can hardly be realised.

The advantages that have been put forward have so far only been described beyond the national level for Europe as avoiding traditional military conflicts. Europe should have become a continent of inner peace. **However, negative goals, such as avoiding military conflicts, do not form credible goals in the long run. They devalue themselves over time.**

When the transfer payments to avoid hard economic conflicts finally approach the costs of an economic war, the fiction of an all-serving political community collapses. This is where Europe has now reached with its excessive government debt.

This is why another fiction has recently been put forward, above all by the German political class: Without a far-reaching political unity of Europe, this particular area of

civilization will lose its influence in the global power game in the future. The answer to the question, which of the foreseeable changes in the world could or even should be influenced in the elementary interest of Europe and for what a price, remains unanswered by the political class, not only in Germany but throughout Europe.

Yes, this cardinal question does not seem to be asked at all, neither politically nor intellectually. That is why the impression is growing the European politicians are really only concerned with their respective short-term retention of power.

We have been witnessing a growing disenchantment with parties for some time now, but not a general disenchantment with politics. Quite the opposite. Resistance to the European model of party rule has grown. And it does not take a great deal of foresight to see that the uprising of citizens, but not of opposition party groups on the fringes of Europe, especially in the peripheral regions of North Africa and the Middle East, will soon set an example for the centre, namely the core countries of the European Union. Revolutions always start at the edges before they reach the centers of power.

There is a fundamental political deficit today. There is no detailed European vision of the future, which would describe the living conditions of Europeans and the societies surrounding them in a global comparison, at least up to the generation after next. Nor are the burdens for clearly defined groups of the population described, which a European state structure may impose on them at the most. Such a setting of the absolute exposure limits would also be an effective precaution against state-driven devaluation of money. For a falling purchasing power of the currency would then automatically result in a real reduction of the share the state could skim off from the added value of its citizens.

It is simply not enough to set minimum social standards and to keep raising them, if at the same time the limits for economic burdens and restrictions on the personal way of life are not set, which must not be exceeded for any citizen. A state debt limit in the constitution must be supplemented by an individual burden limit for citizens, which must also be laid down in the constitution. Otherwise, the politically defined precariat, which has since been declared the primary goal of political action, will completely determine our future. Where would that end? *Bread and games* so far have destroyed every civilization. They must therefore be made a private matter, not a state purpose.

HOMO BILLIONIS AS HIS OWN COMPETITOR

SO LET'S GO BACK TO VARUS: Quinctilius Varus may have been convinced that he had to eliminate the errant Germanic fighters. At that time, their residual risk seemed no longer tenable then.

The fact that Varus risked his own legions and with them the whole Roman project *Germania* should lead us to more foresight and to a cool consideration of our goals, not only to a consideration of the supposedly available means. Because our future is not a play of colors between green-red, black-yellow, Jamaica or any other combination of

parties. Parties represent temporary opinions. They almost always reflect the “here and now” of a largely uninformed majority. The current call for global sustainability is reminiscent of the dinosaurs’ silent hope that the world should not change so that their way of life is preserved. Our future is really a question of our intellectual, not our state constitution. It must allow the uncomfortable, even the unthinkable horizons, and find effective, inescapably selfish answers. What counts is success or failure in adapting to a reality that we have found and that we will only change very limitedly and very slowly? This reality is the *homo billionis*⁷ that grows anew with each generation, always since its archaic beginning, a product of evolution shaped by a selection process that leaves only those few who are able to escape the pull of the herd - and that means: those who follow their mind, but not their feelings.

The conclusion is:

1. The global population is too large to ever restore or even maintain the pre-industrial natural state in its basic structure.
2. For this reason, there is no point in striving for global political unity in order to pursue an unattainable goal.
3. Those who have the means to adapt to the changes in the ecosphere that are already underway, must organize themselves accordingly. A global “watering can” principle will only fuel the conflicts instead of dampening them.

What is surprising about our current situation and seems deeply disturbing is that the *homo billionis* suddenly faces himself in an existential and truly global crowding-out competition, no longer nature. “Nature” is more or less destabilized and needs human “help” because it can no longer sustain itself and at the same time “carry” billions of people. In such a critical situation, the future development of human societies must be reconsidered.

⁷ I also described this term in detail in my article: Sassin, Wolfgang. 2018. “Die Transformation des sozialen Bewusstseins.” *The Beacon: Journal for Studying Ideologies and Mental Dimensions* 1, 010210201.

REFERENCES

- Cassius Dio. 1987. *The Roman History: The Reign of Augustus*. Transl. by Ian Scott-Kilvert, with an introduction of John Carter. London: Penguin Classics.
- Häfele, Wolf, Anderer, Jeanne, McDonald, Alan, and Nebojsa Nakicenovic. 1981. *Energy in a Finite World*. Vol. 1: Paths to a Sustainable Future. Vol. 2: A Global Systems Analysis. Cambridge, MA: Ballinger Publishing Co.
- Häfele, Wolf, and Wolfgang Sassin. 1976. "Energy strategies." *Energy* 1, no. 2: 147–163. DOI: 10.1016/0360-5442(76)90014-1
- Häfele, Wolf, and Wolfgang Sassin. 1978. "Energy Options and Strategies for Western Europe." *Science* 200, no. 4338: 164–167.
- Häfele, Wolf, and Wolfgang Sassin. 1979. "The global energy system." *Systems Research* 24, no. 3: 169–189. DOI: 10.1002/bs.3830240303
- Lovelock, James. 2016. *Gaia: A New Look at Life on Earth*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Sassin, Wolfgang. 2012. "Was die Staatsschulden-Krisen uns lehren? Es gibt kein Perpetuum mobile für Ökonomie, Ökologie und soziale Entwicklung." *Das Gespräch aus der Ferne*, no. 398. In German.
- Sassin, Wolfgang. 2015. "Alternativlos? Um seine Stellung in der Welt zu sichern, muss Europa sich neu erfinden." *Das Gespräch aus der Ferne*, no. 402: 22–27. In German.
- Sassin, Wolfgang, Donskikh, Oleg, Gnes, Alexandre, Komissarov, Sergey, and Depei Liu. 2018. *Evolutionary Environments. Homo Sapiens - an Endangered Species?* Innsbruck: Studia Universitätsverlag.
- WBGU. 2011. *Welt im Wandel: Gesellschaftsvertrag für eine Große Transformation: Hauptgutachten*. Berlin: Wissenschaftlicher Beirat d. Bundesregierung Globale Umweltveränderungen. In German.
- Wells, Herbert George. 2018. *The Time Machine*. 1st edition in 1895. Lonson: SeaWolf.

EXTENDED SUMMARY

SASSIN, WOLFGANG. DEJA VUE?

EARLIER CIVILIZATIONS WERE DEPENDENT ON THE WIDE AVAILABILITY OF BIOMASS, HYDROPOWER, WIND ENERGY, HUMAN AND ANIMAL LABOUR. That was true until modern times. The industrial revolution and modernity relied on coal, later on mineral oil and natural gas. Fossil energies seemed almost inexhaustible at the beginning of the industrial revolution. This „revolution“ was, strictly speaking, the second major energy revolution since the beginning of agriculture at the end of the Stone Age. It expanded human possibilities in an unexpected way. Starting from England, first Western Europe, later the United States, Russia and Japan

finally began to exert truly global influence with the help of the new civilization means that became accessible by ever new powerful energy forms. The prerequisite for the emergence of overarching large power structures was no longer the spatial expansion of a system of rule with the aim of attracting additional human labour for civil and military projects. The growth of industrial civilization needed access to fossil energy deposits, which are rather unevenly distributed globally. To a lesser extent, the same was true for those raw materials that were or are necessary for the construction of the material infrastructure and the technical artefacts of an industrial civilization: ores, phosphates, etc.

Today's industrial civilization is essentially a hybrid between classic great empires and a society based on mechanical slaves. In the multipolar world of the present, great political "empires" are confronted with each other in an existential competition. The substructure of these "great empires," i.e. their "mechanical slaves," feed on technical energy. The reproduction behavior of this substructure is similar to that of ants or termites. As with the "queens" of these peoples, there are only a few large production complexes that can generate such modern slaves. The greater the number of slaves that are necessary to fuel a state, the lower the reproduction rate of these slaves.

The well-being and the performance of modern "queens with court" in "developed" countries therefore determine the sustainability and the level of power these empires can exercise. In this context, it cannot be indicated clearly enough that the transformation of the world into industrialized and developing countries and the resulting power gap only arose through the transformation of a few agricultural societies into industrial societies.

Modern Europe need be clear enough about which of the mutually exclusive civilization states we want to join and what the consequences may be, because it's not just about technical decisions, such as an energy turnaround or the survival of certain currencies. Rather, the question is whether European countries can start such a basic experiment that cannot be stopped halfway through, and which will determine Europe's chances in a world that usually does not tolerate mistakes. In this paper the possible outcomes for Europe and in particular Germany are analyzed on the basis of ideologies and civilization choices adopted thus far. The fact that our civilization is faced with a decision which at first sight seems purely tactical, as it once did when Publius Quinctilius Varus decided to control „wild“ Germania with his troops which were dependent on a highly efficient infrastructure, must in fact shatter the foundations of the dominant political powers of today. A functioning and technically controllable energy infrastructure form the indispensable foundation of every form of modern civilization.

Because of the basic prerequisites for a redistribution of the planetary bases of life according to scientific models, the goal of which is to maintain certain climatic conditions and self-regenerating biological cycles, the following highly unusual conditions must be considered by European politicians in the future: 1. Existential advantages and disadvantages on Planet Earth could no longer be defended or corrected by military actions. Instead they had to be compensated by peaceful transfers of energy, raw materials, knowledge and by resettlement of populations. That would not be an economic exchange via markets, but by a forced altruism to be planned centrally and ultimately accepted without resistance. 2. Efficiencies in the use of production factors would have to be monitored just as strictly as monitoring consumer goods and its strict ecological control. That will inevitably require ideocracy. 3. Individual freedom in shaping the way of dealing with the natural foundations of life and the need to protect these foundations in favor of global

use, are mutually exclusive and would simply have to be accepted as a welcome intellectual compromise.

The inevitable conclusion, therefore, is:

1. The global population is too large to ever restore a pre-industrial natural status or even maintain the basic structure of the present culturally modified ecosystem, including climate.

2. For this reason, there is no point in striving for global political unity in order to pursue an unattainable goal.

3. Those who have the means to adapt to the changes in the ecosphere that are already underway must organize themselves accordingly. A global “watering can principle” will only fuel regional and global conflicts instead of dampening them.

Author / Авторъ

Dr-Ing Wolfgang Sassin’s teaching, research, advisory activities and affiliations included the Technical University of Vienna (Austria), the Research Centre Jülich (Germany), IIASA (Austria), the International Panel on Climate Change IPCC, the UN Program Habitat, the Directorate General on Research and Innovation of the European Commission (Belgium), and OEMs in the German automobile industry on man-machine interfaces.

Wolfgang Sassin,

Independent researcher,
Jochberg 5
6335 Thiersee
Austria

© Wolfgang Sassin

Licensee The Beacon: Journal for Studying Ideologies and Mental Dimensions

Licensing the materials published is made according to Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) licence

